

LOCAL CONTEXTS

RESTORING SOVEREIGNTY WITH PLANT RELATIVES

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CBIKS | Center for Braiding Indigenous Knowledges and Science

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TO LEARN MORE ABOUT LOCAL CONTEXTS LABELS, VISIT [HTTPS://LOCALCONTEXTS.ORG](https://localcontexts.org) AND THE U.S. NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION CENTER FOR BRAIDING INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGES AND SCIENCE (NSF CBIKS): [WWW.UMASS.EDU/GATEWAY/RESEARCH/INDIGENOUS-KNOWLEDGES](http://www.umass.edu/gateway/research/indigenous-knowledges)

THE U.S. NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION CENTER FOR BRAIDING INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGES AND SCIENCE (NSF CBIKS) EXAMINES HOW TO EFFECTIVELY AND ETHICALLY BRAID INDIGENOUS AND WESTERN SCIENCE RESEARCH, EDUCATION, AND PRACTICE RELATED TO THE URGENT AND INTERCONNECTED CHALLENGES OF ENVIRONMENTAL ADAPTATION, PROTECTION AND CARE OF CULTURAL PLACES, AND FOOD SECURITY. OUR PLACE-BASED RESEARCH IS COMMUNITY-DRIVEN, CARRIED OUT IN FULL COLLABORATION WITH OUR INDIGENOUS COMMUNITY PARTNERS IN 8 HUBS ACROSS THE U.S., CANADA, AOTEAROA/NEW ZEALAND, AND AUSTRALIA.

NSF CBIKS AIMS TO UNDERSTAND HOW TO BRAID INDIGENOUS AND WESTERN KNOWLEDGE AND SCIENCE PRACTICES AT EACH PHASE OF THE RESEARCH PROCESS. WE DO THIS THROUGH THE 7 THEMATIC AREAS YOU SEE IN THIS INDIGENOUS RESEARCH CIRCLE. OUR THEMATIC RESEARCH DRAWS KEY LESSONS FROM PLACE-BASED PROJECTS CARRIED OUT IN CBIKS' 8 REGIONAL HUBS AND SHARE THOSE INSIGHTS TO STRENGTHEN ETHICAL UNIVERSITY-COMMUNITY PARTNERSHIPS.

OUR RESEARCH PROCESS CENTERS RELATIONALITY AND ETHICS. WE FOCUS ON DATA SOVEREIGNTY AND HOW TO CARE FOR THE KNOWLEDGE PRODUCED PRIOR TO AND THROUGHOUT THE RESEARCH PROCESS. THIS INVOLVES DETERMINING APPROPRIATE USE/ACCESS OF KNOWLEDGE, MATERIALS, SAMPLES; AND DEVELOPING INDIGENOUS DATA MANAGEMENT PLANS TO MEET COMMUNITY NEEDS. IN EACH HUB'S PLACE-BASED STUDY FIELDWORK, WE CONSIDER HOW TO ETHICALLY BRAID WESTERN AND INDIGENOUS DATA, INCLUDING TRADITIONAL ECOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE. THROUGH STORYWORK AND KNOWLEDGE MOBILIZATION WE ENSURE THAT THE NEW KNOWLEDGE WE PRODUCE IS APPROPRIATELY SHARED AND ACCESSIBLE BY INDIGENOUS COMMUNITY PARTNERS, THE SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY, AND THE PUBLIC. THIS SCIENCE COMMUNICATION INVOLVES STORYTELLING AND ARTS-BASED METHODS SUCH AS THIS INFOGRAPHIC, OR COMICS, ANIMATIONS, OR STORYBASKETS. FORMAL AND INFORMAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING SCIENTISTS ARE ESSENTIAL NSF CBIKS EDUCATION ACTIVITIES. WE PROVIDE K-12 CAMPS AND AFTERSCHOOL PROGRAMMING, TEACHER TRAINING, AND ONLINE LEARNING BUNDLES AVAILABLE THROUGH MITX. WE SUPPORT POLICY AND GOVERNMENT AGENCIES BY SHARING OUR RESEARCH SO IT CAN IMPACT THE SUSTAINABLE CARE OF NATURAL AND CULTURAL RESOURCES.

WHAT ARE THE LOCAL CONTEXTS LABELS?

THE TRADITIONAL KNOWLEDGE (TK) AND BIOCULTURAL (BC) LABELS ARE TOOLS FOR INDIGENOUS COMMUNITIES AND LOCAL ORGANIZATIONS. DEVELOPED THROUGH SUSTAINED PARTNERSHIP AND TESTING WITHIN INDIGENOUS COMMUNITIES ACROSS MULTIPLE COUNTRIES, THE LABELS ALLOW COMMUNITIES TO EXPRESS LOCAL AND SPECIFIC CONDITIONS FOR SHARING AND ENGAGING IN FUTURE RESEARCH AND RELATIONSHIPS IN WAYS THAT ARE CONSISTENT WITH ALREADY EXISTING COMMUNITY RULES, GOVERNANCE, AND PROTOCOLS FOR USING, SHARING, AND CIRCULATING KNOWLEDGE AND DATA. LABELS CAN BE APPLIED TO WEBSITES, PUBLICATIONS, DATASETS, MUSEUM EXHIBITIONS, ITEMS IN A COLLECTION, GENETIC SAMPLES, AND MORE. COMMUNITIES CAN CUSTOMIZE AND APPLY THEIR TK AND BC LABELS USING THE LOCAL CONTEXTS HUB WEBSITE.

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